

The Development and Validation of a Measurement Instrument for Assessing Empathy and Cultural Diversity in a Spanish Context.

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Abstract

The Everyday Multicultural Competencies/Revised Scale of Ethnocultural Empathy (EMC/RSEE) assesses various dimensions related to intercultural interactions, including cultural openness, awareness of racism, empathy, resentment, and anxiety. The adaptation and validation of the EMC/RSEE in a Spanish sample will provide a valuable tool for researchers and practitioners interested in measuring intercultural competence in Spain, particularly in educational settings.

A total of 533 multilingual students, all native Spanish, participated in this study, recruited from various Spanish universities ranging in age from 18 to 55 years ($M = 22.47$; $SD = 4.59$). The internal consistency and a Confirmatory Factor Analysis were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics v.29 and EQS 6.4. The internal consistency indices for each dimension are similar to those reported in Finck et al. (2021). The 5-factor model proposed by them falls short of the desired threshold in SEM fit indices, and a second-order two-factor model is also inadequate too.

Rather than a single scale with 5 dimensions, it appears that we are dealing with two scales: a "Cultural and Empathic Engagement" scale with a positive orientation towards different cultures, and a "Cultural Tension and Self-Efficacy Concerns" scale with a more negative orientation.

Keywords: Scale of Ethnocultural Empathy; Validation; Empathy; Cultural Diversity; Spain.

Introduction

According to the Instituto Nacional de Estadística - INE (2024), the Spanish population reached 48,592,909 citizens, marking the highest population value in the historical series on an annual basis. This increase can be primarily attributed to the rise in the number of immigrants, which now totals 6,491,502. Presently, it is undeniable that Spain has become a country of immigration, entering a second migration cycle since 2018. Consequently, migration has re-emerged as a significant topic of debate on the country's public and political agenda (Pinyol-Jiménez & Perez-Ramírez, 2022) and has garnered considerable interest, concern, and public discourse in Spain. Since the mid-1990s, Spain has evolved into a major destination for individuals from North Africa, America, Eastern Europe, and other regions (Reher et al., 2008). Notably, a substantial portion of this immigrant population is concentrated in younger age groups, with the majority falling within the 20 to 44 age brackets. Approximately 20% of foreigners residing in Spain are minors, subject to compulsory schooling, while the remainder constitutes the potential workforce. A high flow of immigration composed of students and workers generates various societal needs, including the expansion and adaptation of educational curricula to accommodate the increased demand. Additionally, implementing cultural and linguistic integration programs is essential to facilitate their adaptation and full participation in the community. If these new requirements are overlooked, there is a significant risk of social exclusion for both groups, which can lead to broader social and economic challenges.

On the other side, a rapid multilingual society has emerged with the need to develop proper attitudes for locals towards other ethnic groups and the subsequent educational deployment for both educators and learners. *Cultural empathy* (Ivey et al., 1987; Ridley & Lingle, 1996), *empathetic multicultural awareness* (Junn et al., 1995), *cultural role taking* (Scott & Borodovsky, 1990), *ethnic perspective taking* (Quintana et al., 2000),

ethnotherapeutic empathy (Parson, 1993), or *Intercultural Competence* (IC) are some of the terms used in the literature to refer to the management of intercultural empathy, which would facilitate societal understanding. Finck et al. (2021) used *Intercultural Competence* to refer to the skills, knowledge and attitudes to successfully interact in intercultural settings, and again, noticed the wide variety of terms used to describe IC in the literature: “cultural intelligence, intercultural capability, cross cultural capability (Presbitero, 2016), cultural knowledge, cultural schemas (Chua et al., 2012), negotiating reality (Friedman & Antal, 2005), multicultural awareness and multicultural effectiveness (Van Oudenhoven & Van Der Zee, 2002)”, etc. According to (Barrett, 2013), IC enables individuals to respond appropriately, effectively, and respectfully, fostering the establishment of constructive relationships. All these terms would also stem from different theoretical models, such as (Byram, 2021; Deardorff, 2006), etc., with their corresponding measuring tools. Surprisingly, many theoretical accounts overlook the impact of empathy on intercultural situations.

The first and most widely accepted tool for measuring empathy toward people from different racial and ethnic backgrounds was developed by (Wang et al., 2003). The Scale of Ethnocultural Empathy (SEE) underwent exploratory and factor analyses, resulting in a four-factor model: 1) Empathic feeling and expression; 2) Empathic perspective taking; 3) acceptance of cultural differences; and 4) Empathic awareness. Wang et al. (2003) considered empathy, whether by nature or nurture, to be a key phenomenon for prosocial behavior (Hoffman, 2000) and intergroup or racial conflict avoidance (Struch & Schwartz, 1989). Most perspectives on defining cultural empathy encompass either a developmental consideration (Quintana et al., 1999) or an ability (Ridley & Lingle, 1996). Consequently, ethnocultural empathy, whether a learned ability or a personal trait, "can be assessed" (Wang et al., 2003, p. 222), and the outcomes of such assessments can

be valid for diagnosing attitudes toward other groups and developing subsequent educational measures. Wang et al.'s scale has been validated for Swedish (Rasoal et al., 2011), Italian (Albiero & Matricardi, 2013), and Spanish (Albar et al., 2015) users, confirming the same factorial structure. However, in the case of the Spanish version, the sample comprised first-year nursing students, making it unsuitable for applications in educational sciences or teaching contexts.

Based on Miville-Guzman Universality Diversity Scale, shortened version - MGUDS-S (Fuertes et al., 2000) the Openness to Diversity/Challenge Scale – ODCS (Pascarella et al., 1996) and the Scale of Ethnocultural Empathy (Wang et al., 2003), Mallinckrodt et al. (2014) designed the Everyday Multicultural Competencies/Revised Scale of Ethnocultural Empathy - EMC/RSEE. This tool aimed to widen the perspective of the previous instruments by including measures of skills, attitudes and knowledge of intercultural competence and ethnocultural empathy that were included in multicultural education and training programs. The scale was applied in a sample of White university students in the USA and resulted in a six-factor model: 1) Cultural openness and desire to learn; 2) Resentment and cultural dominance; 3) Anxiety and lack of multicultural self-efficacy; 4) Empathic perspective-taking; 5) Awareness of contemporary racism and privilege; 6) Empathic feeling and acting as an ally.

Drawing from Mallinckrodt et al.'s scale (2014), Finck et al. (2021) validated the Everyday Multicultural Competencies Scale/Revised Scale of Ethnocultural Empathy - EMC/RSEE in Spanish. This validation involved a diverse sample of undergraduate students from various academic disciplines, including management and psychology. The scale presented a five-factor model comprising: 1) Cultural openness; 2) Conscience of racism; 3) Empathy; 4) Resentment; 5) Anxiety. The context was Colombia, a Latin American country with "its particular social, historical, cultural and economic features"

(Finck et al., 2021 p. 165). Ethnicity, cultural diversity, social division and exclusion, and economic inequality are features that suggest the scale's usability "in the wider Spanish-speaking context of Latin America" (Finck et al., 2021 p. 165).

There is a clear need to adapt the scale for the education field, particularly for the population responsible for educating new generations. This paper aims to provide such a tool by adapting and validating the EMC/RSEE in Spanish for the context of Spain.

Method

Participants

A total of 533 multilingual students participated in this study, recruited from various Spanish universities (Huelva, Oviedo, Málaga, Polytechnic University of Madrid, Cádiz, Granada, Rey Juan Carlos, Alicante, Almería, Cáceres, Castilla-La Mancha, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, UOC, Valladolid, and Zaragoza). The sample consisted of 398 women (74.5%) and 129 men (24.2%), with 6 individuals identifying as "Non-Cis" (1.1%), ranging in age from 18 to 55 years ($M = 22.47$; $SD = 4.59$). All participants reported Spanish as their native language.

A significant proportion of the participants, 54.7% ($n = 292$), were multilingual, speaking an average of 4.3 additional languages. Specifically, 114 participants (21.3%) spoke 4 additional languages, and 102 participants (19.1%) spoke 5 or more additional languages.

It is important to note that only 47 participants (8.8%) had previous volunteer experience with immigrant populations.

Instruments

A Spanish adaptation of the "Everyday Multicultural Competencies Scale / Revised Scale of Ethnocultural Empathy (EMC/RSEE)" was used. This instrument was originally translated, adapted, and validated for a population of Colombian university students in urban areas by Finck et al. (2021). The original scale consists of 48 items with a 6-point Likert scale (1: Strongly disagree, to 6: Strongly agree), distributed across 6 dimensions or factors: "Cultural Openness and Desire to Learn" (henceforth referred to as "Cultural Openness"), "Resentment and Cultural Dominance" (henceforth referred to as "Resentment"), "Anxiety and Lack of Multicultural Self-Efficacy" ("Anxiety"), "Empathic Perspective-Taking" ("Empathic Perspective-Taking"), "Awareness of Contemporary Racism and Privilege" (henceforth referred to as "Awareness of Racism"), and "Empathic Feeling and Acting as an Ally" ("Empathic Feeling").

For the adaptation into Colombian Spanish, a forward-backward translation procedure was carried out with native Spanish (Colombian) speakers and foreigners with a high level of Spanish. Following the translation and back-translation process, a panel of experts analyzed the items and suggested that the item "I don't understand why minority groups need their own television channels" be discarded. This was due to the absence of specific television channels or similar media for ethnic minorities in the Colombian context, and its exclusion from the Spanish adaptation for the same reason. The panel also requested minor linguistic adjustments to the item set. Some items that referred specifically to the US were modified to be suitable for other audiences by replacing "US" with the Spanish equivalent of "my country". Similarly, the nouns "Americans" and "white people in the US" were changed to "people in my country" to ensure consistency with the previous items; also, the noun "the minority" was changed to "minority groups".

Results from the Colombian adaptation of the six-factor model proposed by Mallinckrodt et al. (2014) indicated that the overall model did not exhibit good fit indices, although the chi-square to degrees of freedom ratio ($2518, 1019 \text{ df} = 2.47 < 3$) and the RMSEA value ($0.0551 < .08$) were acceptable. However, the CFI = 0.79 and TLI = 0.787 did not reach the required level of 0.9 for a good model fit, suggesting a five-factor structure where the items from "Empathic feeling and acting as an ally" and "Empathic perspective-taking" were combined into a single factor (Empathy) and items that did not fit adequately were removed (6 items in total), resulting in a 41-item scale with more suitable fit indices: chi-square ($1996, 769 \text{ df} = 2.59 < 3$), CFI = .817, TLI = .805, RMSEA = .0574.

Data analysis

Data analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics v.29 (IBM, 2023) and EQS 6.4 (Bentler & Wu, 2016). Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was performed using EQS 6.4, employing the robust Satorra-Bentler chi-square statistic (Chou et al., 1991; Kline, 2023; Ullman, 1996). Robust goodness-of-fit indices, such as the Normed Fit Index (NFI), Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI), and Comparative Fit Index (CFI) (Bentler, 1990), were used, with values of .9 or higher indicating excellent fit. The root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) was also calculated, with values below .08 suggesting good fit (Steiger, 2016). Internal consistency reliability, for both subscales and the overall scale(s), was assessed using Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega.

Results

Internal Consistency

Initially, an internal consistency analysis was conducted using Cronbach's alpha, yielding a value of .75 for the full scale. McDonald's omega coefficient could not be calculated

for the full scale due to a dimension loading negatively on the rest, as will be shown later in the confirmatory factor analysis. The internal consistency indices for each dimension can be found in Table 1, which are similar to those reported in Finck et al. (2021).

Table 1: Internal consistency analysis

	α	Ω	Items	Finck et al.	
				α	Ω
Cultural Openness and Desire to Learn	.870	.873	10	.86	.88
Resentment and Cultural Dominance	.823	.825	7	.85	.86
Anxiety and Lack of Multicultural Self-Efficacy	.708	.710	5	.76	.76
Empathic Perspective-Taking and Acting as an Ally	.774	.769	11	.77	.77
Awareness of Contemporary Racism and Privilege	.777	.779	8	.75	.76

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

The 5-factor model proposed by Finck et al. (2021) for assessing multicultural competence and ethnocultural empathy is tested, as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The 5-factor model path diagram proposed by Finck et al. (2021) and tested in this study.

Table 2. Model Fit Indices for Individual Subscales and the Total Scale

	Cultural Openness	Empathy*	Awareness of racism**	Resent.	Anxiety	Total Scale
SB - χ^2	116.4248	97.4782	63.5819	435.438	81.545	1398.6412
	(p < .001)	(p < .001)	(p < .001)	(p < .001)	(p = .14792)	(p < .001)
BBNFI	.920	.897	.920	.947	.964	.811
BBNNFI	.926	.911	.904	.945	.971	.872

CFI	.943	.931	.936	.963	.985	.880
RMSEA	.066	.058	.081	.063	.034	.044
90% IC	(.053, .079)	(.044, .071)	(.062, .102)	(.042, .084)	(.000, .075)	(.041, .047)
α	.870	.762	.741	.822	.708	.711
ρ	.873	.766	.752	.826	.712	.800

* EMP_10_1 deleted
** AWR_34 deleted

While the individual subscales demonstrate excellent fit indices (Table 2), the overall scale fit indices fall short of the desired threshold in SEM ($> .95$), with the exception of the RMSEA ($< .08$). To address this issue, a second-order two-factor model is proposed and tested, as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The 2 second order factor model path diagram tested in this study.

As can be observed in Table 3, the fit indices of the total scale with the two second-order factors are also inadequate ($< .95$), except for the RMSEA. However, when grouping the subscales “Cultural Openness and Desire to Learn”, “Empathic Perspective-Taking and Acting as an-Ally”, and “Awareness of Contemporary Racism and Privilege”, the fit indices improve. Similarly, grouping the subscales “Resentment and Cultural Dominance” and “Anxiety and Lack of Multicultural Self-Efficacy” also yields adequate fit indices. Therefore, rather than a single scale with 5 dimensions, it appears that we are

dealing with two scales: a "Cultural and Empathic Engagement" scale with a positive orientation towards different cultures, and a "Cultural Tension and Self-Efficacy Concerns" scale with a more negative orientation.

Table 3. Fit Indices for Two Second Order Scale, and for Individual Independent Subscales.

	CO+E+AR	Res+Ans	Total Scale
SB - χ^2	731.6465 (p < .001)	113.0238 (p < .001)	1594.6807 (p < .001)
BBNFI	.902	.913	.801
BBNNFI	.934	.937	.868
CFI	.922	.950	.876
RMSEA	.049	.047	.043
90% IC	(.044, .054)	(.035, .059)	(.040, .046)
α	.898	.854	.718
ρ	.908	.866	.797

* EMP_10_I deleted

** AWR_34 deleted

Based on the analysis of the results, Table 4 illustrates the resulting scale. The positive dimensions—Cultural Openness and Desire to Learn, Empathy, and Awareness of Contemporary Racism and Privilege—form one cluster for analysis, while the negative dimensions—Resentment and Cultural Dominance and Anxiety and Lack of Multicultural Empathy—constitute a second cluster. This clustering provides a clear framework for understanding the dynamics of the analyzed data.

Table 4: Spanish adaptation of the Everyday Multicultural Competencies Scale / Revised Scale of Ethnocultural Empathy (EMC/RSEE)

Item	Subsc.	Statement
1	(C.O.)	Pienso que es importante educarse sobre culturas y países distintos a los míos
7	(C.O.)	Estoy abierto/a a la posibilidad de que conocer una cultura pueda tener una profunda influencia positiva en mí
13	(C.O.)	Admiro la belleza en otras culturas
19	(C.O.)	Me gustaría trabajar en una organización donde consiga trabajar con individuos de diversos orígenes
25	(C.O.)	Me gustaría cenar en la casa de alguien que sea de una cultura diferente
31	(C.O.)	Estoy interesado/a en participar en varias actividades culturales en el campus universitario
36	(C.O.)	La mayoría de la gente de mi país estaría mejor si supiera más sobre las culturas de otros países
41	(C.O.)	Una educación realmente buena requiere saber cómo comunicarse con alguien en otra cultura
45	(C.O.)	Estoy abierto/a a ser influenciado/a por otras culturas (a través del contacto con personas de otras culturas)
47	(C.O.)	Creo mi país es mejorado por otras culturas
4	(E.)	Es fácil para mí entender lo que se sentiría ser una persona de otro origen cultural o étnico diferente al mío
10*	(E.)	Es difícil para mí ponerme en la piel de alguien que es cultural y/o étnicamente diferente a mí (INV)
12	(E.)	Me perturba cuando otras personas experimentan desgracias debido a su origen cultural o étnico

16	(E.)	Es difícil para mí relacionarme con historias que la gente relata sobre la discriminación cultural o étnica que experimenta en su día a día (INV)
18	(E.)	Me conmueven las películas o libros sobre problemas de discriminación que enfrentan los grupos culturales o étnicos diferentes a los míos
22	(E.)	Puedo relacionarme con la frustración que algunas personas sienten por tener menos oportunidades debido a sus orígenes culturales o étnicos.
24	(E.)	Comparto la ira de las personas que son víctimas de crímenes de odio (por ejemplo, violencia intencional debida a la cultura o a la etnia)
30	(E.)	Rara vez pienso en el impacto de una broma racista o étnica en los sentimientos de las personas que son su blanco (INV)
35	(E.)	Cuando escucho a la gente hacer bromas racistas, les digo que me ofenden, aunque no se estén refiriendo a mi grupo cultural o étnico
40	(E.)	Cuando veo a personas que vienen de un origen cultural o étnico diferente triunfar en el ámbito público, comparto su orgullo
44	(E.)	Cuando sé que mis amistades son tratadas injustamente debido a sus orígenes culturales o étnicos, los defiendo
5	(A.R.)	Mi país tiene un largo camino que recorrer antes de que todos y todas sean verdaderamente tratados igual
11	(A.R.)	Para dos bebés nacidos con el mismo potencial en mi país hoy en día, en general todavía es más difícil tener éxito para un niño/a de color que para un niño/a blanco/a
17	(A.R.)	Soy consciente de cómo otros grupos raciales o étnicos son oprimidos sistemáticamente en nuestra sociedad
23	(A.R.)	Hoy en mi país, las personas blancas todavía tienen muchas ventajas importantes en comparación con otros grupos étnicos
29	(A.R.)	Soy consciente de cómo la sociedad trata de forma diferente a grupos culturales o étnicos diferentes a los míos
34*	(A.R.)	Soy consciente de las barreras institucionales (por ejemplo, oportunidades restringidas para el ascenso en el trabajo) que discriminan contra grupos culturales o étnicos diferentes a los míos
39	(A.R.)	El racismo es más que todo una cosa del pasado (INV)
43	(A.R.)	En mi país todo el mundo tiene una oportunidad igual de éxito (INV)
2	(R.)	Los miembros de grupos minoritarios tienden a exaltarse todo el tiempo
8	(R.)	Estando en mi país, las minorías deberían hacer un esfuerzo para integrarse en nuestra cultura
20	(R.)	No entiendo por qué los miembros de grupos minoritarios se quejan de ser aislados de la sociedad
26	(R.)	Me siento irritado/a cuando personas de diferentes orígenes culturales o étnicos hablan su idioma a mí alrededor
32	(R.)	Las minorías ingresan al colegio con mayor facilidad y algunos terminan con mínimo esfuerzo
37	(R.)	Estoy preocupado/a de que las personas de mi país pronto se conviertan en una minoría debido a tantos inmigrantes
46	(R.)	Pienso que los miembros de grupos minoritarios culpan demasiado a otros por sus desgracias
3	(A.)	Me siento incómodo/a al interactuar con personas de diferentes culturas
9	(A.)	A menudo me encuentro temeroso/a de personas de otras razas
15	(A.)	Dudo que pueda tener una amistad profunda o fuerte con personas que son culturalmente diferentes
21	(A.)	Realmente no sé cómo entablar una amistad con alguien de una cultura diferente
27	(A.)	Temo que las experiencias culturales podrían arriesgarme a perder mi propia identidad

C.O.: Cultural Openness and Desire to Learn; E.: Empathy; A.R.: Awareness of Contemporary Racism and Privilege; R.: Resentment and Cultural Dominance; A.: Anxiety and Lack of Multicultural Self-Efficacy;

*Grayed-out items were removed due to high covariation with other items in the same subscale.

Discussion and conclusions

Understanding the various theoretical models of intercultural competence is fundamental for advancing research and practice in this field. The models of Deardorff (2006), which emphasizes a broad spectrum of intercultural competencies, and Byram (2021), which has a more focused approach on the process of intercultural learning and communication, offer valuable conceptual frameworks for analyzing intercultural competence and designing effective educational interventions. However, it is important to recognize that

neither of these models is exhaustive and that intercultural competence is a constantly evolving construct that is dependent on the specific cultural context. The diversity of terminology surrounding intercultural competence reflects the richness and complexity of this construct, as well as the evolution of its conceptualization over time. The terms "cultural empathy," "multicultural awareness," and "intercultural sensitivity" are used to describe different aspects of this competence (Ivey et al., 1987; Junn et al., 1995; Parson, 1993; Quintana et al., 2000; Ridley & Lingle, 1996; Scott & Borodovsky, 1990). Understanding the relationships between these terms and their implications for research and practice is essential for promoting interculturality and coexistence in increasingly diverse societies.

To measure intercultural competence, instruments such as the Scale of Ethnocultural Empathy (SEE) by Wang et al. (2003), and the Everyday Multicultural Competencies Scale/Revised Scale of Ethnocultural Empathy (EMC/RSEE) by Mallinckrodt et al. (2014), have been developed. While the SEE primarily measures empathy towards individuals from diverse racial and ethnic backgrounds, the EMC/RSEE assesses a wider range of intercultural competencies, including cultural openness and awareness of cultural differences. The SEE and EMC/RSEE scales, while valuable tools for measuring intercultural competence, have certain limitations. The SEE, while effective in measuring empathy, may not fully capture the cognitive and behavioral aspects of intercultural competence. The EMC/RSEE, though comprehensive, can be complex and may not be equally suitable for all cultural contexts.

To address these, our study has expanded the scope of measurement beyond empathy to include a broader range of intercultural competencies and we have carefully adapted the EMC/RSEE to our specific cultural context, considering the unique cultural nuances and values of our participants.

This study contributes to the ongoing research on the measurement of intercultural competence by examining the factorial structure of the EMC/RSEE scale in the Spanish educational context. Our findings, while partially consistent with previous research (Finck et al., 2021; Ridley & Lingle, 1996; Van Oudenhoven & Van Der Zee, 2002), suggest that the scale may require modifications to account for cultural and contextual differences. The need for further refinement is particularly evident when comparing our results to those obtained in a Colombian sample. These findings underscore the importance of conducting context-specific adaptations of measurement instruments to ensure their validity and reliability.

Our findings further confirm the relevance of intercultural competence in the contemporary Spanish context, characterized by increasing cultural diversity. As suggested by previous studies (Finck et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2003), we found intercultural competence to be a multidimensional construct. However, our research provides novel evidence regarding the factorial structure of this competence in the Spanish context, suggesting the existence of two primary dimensions: cultural engagement and empathy, on one hand, and cultural tension and self-efficacy concerns, on the other. The division of the scale into two second-order factors, "Cultural Engagement and Empathy" and "Cultural Tension and Self-Efficacy Concerns," offers a new perspective on intercultural competence. This finding supports the notion that intercultural competence is not a unidimensional construct but involves both positive aspects (openness, empathy) and negative aspects (resentment, anxiety).

Limitations

While this study provides valuable insights into the measurement of intercultural competence among Spanish university students, several limitations should be noted. The sample size and diversity may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the

study's design does not allow for a direct assessment of the construct validity of the scale. Future research should address these limitations by using larger and more diverse samples and by comparing the scale with other measures of intercultural competence. Overall, the findings of this study support the use of the adapted EMC/RSEE scale, but further research is needed to refine the scale and to explore its applicability in different contexts. Furthermore, the findings of this study have significant implications for research and practice in education. First, the identification of two primary dimensions of intercultural competence provides a solid foundation for the development of more targeted and effective intercultural training programs. Second, the need to adapt the scale to different cultural contexts underscores the importance of conducting validation studies in each specific context.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Additional information

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Ethics Approval and Consent

This study was conducted in compliance with ethical standards. Ethics approval or informed consent was not required, this was confirmed and waived by Dr. Emilio Delgado, COIDESO institution, Universidad de Huelva.

Declaration of author contributions

Author 3 and Author 1: Conceptualization, Methodology.

Author 1 and Author 2: Software, Data curation, Validation.

Author 3: Supervision and correspondence.

All authors: Original draft Writing, Review and Editing.

All co-authors meet criteria for authorship and ensure appropriate acknowledgements made in the manuscript.

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